

Metal chelates of 6-aryl-5-hexene-2,4-diones

P. Venugopalan and K. Krishnankutty*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala-673 635, India

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A series of 6-aryl-5-hexene-2,4-diones and their Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} chelates of composition ML₂ have been synthesised. The metal ion replaces the enol proton of the ligands with the formation of a stable six-membered metal chelate ring involving the dicarbonyl function.

In the metal complexes of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds, the carbonyl groups are directly linked to alkyl/aryl groups¹. Very few reports² exist on the coordination behaviour of the dicarbonyl function directly attached to olefinic (–CH=CH) carbons. Such α,β -unsaturated 1,3-dicarbonyl moieties constitute the major physiologically active constituent of several traditional Indian medicinal plants such as *Curcuma longa* L. (turmeric)³. In continuation of our studies on such biologically important compounds⁴, the present communication reports the synthesis and characterisation of the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes of the 6-aryl-5-hexene-2,4-diones (1a-e).

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- a R₁=R₂=H
- b R₁=H, R₂=OCH₃
- c R₁=H, R₂=OH
- d R₁=OCH₃, R₂=OH
- e R₁=R₂=OCH₃

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Results and Discussion

All the metal complexes are stable and do not contain the anion of the metal salt used for their preparation. Analytical data of the complexes indicate their ML₂ stoichiometry. Though the formation 1d was reported during the synthesis of curcuminoids⁵, no spectral data are available for these 1,3-diketones. Therefore, the UV, IR, NMR and mass spectral data of these compounds are also included while discussing the spectral data of the complexes.

The UV spectra of the ligands showed two broad bands at ~350 and ~260 nm due respectively to the carbonyl chromophore and the conjugated C=C group. In the metal complexes the former band showed a bathochromic shift (5–10 nm) indicating the involvement of the dicarbonyl moiety on complexation.

Infrared spectra of the ligands showed two strong bands at ~1665 (intramolecularly hydrogen bonded acetyl) and 1625 cm⁻¹ (cinnamoyl C=O). The strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding that exist in the compounds is evident from the broad band at 2500–3500 cm⁻¹. Several prominent other bands appeared at 1490–1610 (C=C) and ~970 cm⁻¹ (*trans* –CH=CH–)⁵. Both the carbonyl bands in the free ligand disappeared in the spectra of all the complexes. Instead two new bands appeared at 1590–1630 cm⁻¹ in addition to various $\nu_{C=C}$ vibrations. These bands can be assigned to the stretching of metal bonded carbonyl functions. That the carbonyl groups are involved in metal chelate formation with the replacement of the chelated hydrogen is evident from disappearance of the ligand band at 2500–3500 cm⁻¹ and appearance of two medium intensity bands at 400–450 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu_{M=O}$ vibrations. In the spectra of the complexes in which the ligand bears phenolic OH groups, the presence of a relatively broad band at ~3200 cm⁻¹ (OH) suggests that the phenolic OH groups is not involved in bonding with the metal ion.

The ¹H NMR spectra of compounds 1a-e showed a one proton signal above 16 ppm for the strong intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enol proton. Other signals appeared at δ 6.43–6.68 (methine), 6.86–7.93 (aryl), 7.97–8.09 (olefinic) and ~2.5 (methyl). The phenolic protons of 1c and 1d are at δ 9.62 and 9.47, respectively. The observed coupling constant (~16 Hz) of the olefinic protons suggest the *trans* nature of the cinnamoyl double bond. In the ¹H NMR spectra of the Pd^{II} chelates, the signal at δ ~16 is absent indicating the replacement of the enol proton by metal ion. The phenolic protons of 1c and 1d remained almost unaltered in

the spectra of their complexes which strongly suggests that chelate formation has occurred as in structure 2. Integrated intensities of all the protons agree well with the ML_2 formulation of the complexes.

The ^{13}C NMR spectra of **1a** and **1d** showed two well-separated carbonyl carbon signals at ~ 198 (acetyl) and ~ 190 ppm (cinnamoyl). Other carbon signals appeared at ~ 90 (methine), ~ 127 and ~ 135 (olefinic), ~ 27 (methyl) and six signals at 130–140 ppm (aryl). In the spectrum of the Pd^{II} chelate of **1a**, the methine, alkenyl and aryl carbon signals shifted upfield. The acetylcarbonyl carbon signal shifted downfield whereas the cinnamoylcarbonyl signal showed only a marginal shift as expected of the extended conjugation of the metal chelate ring. However, in the case of the Pd^{II} chelate of **1d**, the methine carbon signal shifted downfield (~ 3 ppm) and the methyl carbon signal showed upfield shift (~ 5 ppm), which shows the influence of phenyl substituents on chelate stability.

The base peak in the mass spectra of all the compounds correspond to the molecular ion $P^+/(P+1)^+$. Other prominent peaks are due to the elimination of CH_3CO , CH_3COCH_2 , CH_3COCH_2CO , $ArCH$, Ar^+ , etc. from the molecular ion. The Cu^{II} chelates of all the compounds showed relatively intense peak at m/z corresponding to $[CuL_2]^+$ in agreement with their formulation. However, the base peaks in all the cases are due to the respective ligand fragments. Several metal containing peaks were also observed.

All the Ni^{II} chelates displayed a broad intense band at $\lambda_{max} \sim 17825\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in their electronic spectra indicating a square-planar geometry. Spectra of the chelates (recorded in pyridine, 10^{-3} M) revealed three medium intensity bands at $\lambda_{max} \sim 7850$, ~ 13000 and $\sim 24000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands are characteristic of octahedral Ni^{II} chelates due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions. The calculated ligand field parameters such as LFSE ($\sim 22.5\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), B ($\sim 790\text{ cm}^{-1}$), β (~ 0.855) and $\beta\%$ (~ 14.5) are in agreement with the octahedral geometry of the pyridine adducts. The Cu^{II} complexes exhibited a broad band at $\lambda_{max} \sim 14750\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating their square-planar geometry which is supported by the observed μ_{eff} values (1.74–1.83 B.M.). Thus the spectral data indicate that the ligands function as monobasic bidentate in their ML_2 complexes in which the metal chelation is through the dicarbonyl oxygens.

Experimental

The 6-aryl-5-hexene-2,4-diones were prepared by condensation of benzaldehyde/substituted benzaldehyde with acetylacetone as outlined below⁵. The product formed by mixing acetylacetone (0.075 mol, 7.5 g) and boric oxide (0.055 mol, 0.375 g) was suspended in dry ethyl acetate (50 ml) containing tri(*s*-butyl)borate (0.1 mol, 23 g). To this mixture, at -0° , a solution of the aromatic aldehyde (0.025

mol) in dry ethyl acetate (15 ml) and *n*-butylamine (0.5 ml) were added dropwise during 90 min with constant stirring. Stirring was further continued for ~ 2 h and the solution was then set aside overnight. The mixture was then stirred for ~ 1 h with hot (50°) hydrochloric acid (0.4 *M*; 20 ml) and extracted repeatedly with ethyl acetate. The combined extracts was uniformly applied on the top of a silica gel (60–120 mesh) column ($2 \times 100\text{ cm}$) and then eluted with a 5 : 1 (v/v) mixture of chloroform-acetone at a uniform flow rate of 2 ml/min. The yellow band developed in the lower region was recovered by successive elution and the combined eluates on evaporation yielded the products (45–50% yield) which were recrystallised from hot benzene : **1a**, m.p. 124° (Found : C, 76.52; H, 6.27. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$ requires : C, 76.60; H, 6.42%), m/z 188 (P^+), 173, 145, 131, 103, 91, 77, 65, 51, 43; **1b**, 131° , m/z 218 (P^+), 203, 200, 185, 175, 161, 147, 133, 115, 103, 89, 77, 63, 51, 43; **1c**, 143° , m/z 234 (P^+), 219, 204, 191, 177, 149. 137, 123, 107, 95, 77, 57, 43; **1d**, 146° , m/z 234 (P^+), 219, 204, 191, 177, 149, 137, 123, 107, 95, 77, 57, 43; **1e**, 155° , m/z 248 (P^+), 266, 233, 218, 205, 191, 178, 165, 151, 142, 137, 122, 107, 93, 77, 60, 43.

Metal complexes : The Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of the diketones were prepared as follows. An aqueous solution of the metal(II) acetate (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of the ligand (0.002 mol) in methanol (15 ml). The mixture was then refluxed for ~ 3 h on a boiling water-bath and then cooled to room temperature. The precipitated product was washed with water, then with ethanol and dried in vacuum. The Pd^{II} complex was prepared using palladium(II) chloride.

C and H were analysed on a Heraeus CHN analyser, and metal percentages by standard procedures. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 8101 A FTIR spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer, NMR spectra a Jeol 400 spectrometer (at R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Mumbai) and mass spectra on a Jeol SX-102 FAB spectrometer (at R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow).

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